

Smart responsive portal towards boosting tourism in North Al Batina

¹Ansaf Rashid Al-issaei, ²Zainab Musabah Al-Rukaini, ³Alsaadah Saif Al-abri, ⁴Arham Mohammed Al-qurri
^{1,2,3,4}University of Technology and Applied Science - Shinas, Oman

¹ 66j1940@shct.edu.om, ² 66j1905@shct.edu.om, ³ 66j19100@shct.edu.om, ⁴ 66j1971@shct.edu.om

Abstract:

This project is a great and distinctive way dedicated to the exhibition of different tourist destinations, spots or places in North Al-Batinah. It can help in boosting the tourism industry in this area specifically. The process of developing tourist attractions in North Al Batinah will become easier and faster through the portal where tourists can access the website anytime and anywhere. They also, can share their suggestions for the better developments and enhancements. In the other hand, the administrative officials and the tour guide can submit tourist recommendations to the competent authorities for consideration and further actions. The system facilitates tourists to contribute in the promotion of tourist places in North Al Batinah. The outcome of the project will impact the following:

1. Showcase the different tourist attractions in the area
2. Facilitate tourists and tour guides to contribute in the promotion of tourist places through typed comments, polls, and smart interactive devices that can be placed in different locations
3. Create better and safe entertainment facilities for residents
4. Attract external tourist from neighboring countries and cities
5. Promote entrepreneurship opportunities for young job seekers and for local women who can run business in the tourist places